

Popcorn, Pizza and Source Code Model of Miyawaki Landscaping.

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Abstract:

BIM architectures are introduced with an online editor to create customized, social forestry, towards food plots for conservation, habitat restoration and defragmentation, towards the conservation of several species of fauna to reduce human-wildlife conflicts.

A simplified model of Miyawaki Landscaping using two or more species of indigenous popcorn and oak trees is introduced as a model of Miyawaki Landscaping , a food plot with edible flora combined with oak acorn based flour towards vegan pizzas and popcorn, with source code for Miyawaki planning and AI4Good.

Keywords: BIM Files, Miyawaki Landscaping, human-wildlife conflicts, AI4Good

Fig 1. ¹ A collection of images linked from a public domain web source, cited below, of Hiroshima, Then and Now, a proof of Akira Miyawaki's philosophy, that nature restores itself, as if human action did not even exist.

<what>

Miyawaki Landscaping is introduced with a 5 layer model, with BIM Templates, which can be edited to customize online.

In the popcorn, pizza and source code model of indigenous landscaping, reconciliation with the indigenous within, in a belonging to the land, as an approach to giving back to the land, a conservation approach to habitat restoration.

This includes Layer 5, Oak Trees of as many Oak species, interspersed with other trees.

Layer 4- Layer 1: flora that forms edible vegetables and biomass for human and fauna.

Layer 2: Grasses, including a biodiverse mix of indigenous corn, pop corn species and several other wild grass seeds.

This is implemented on the Mother Divine Website as an architecture service with turn key implementations with an implementation partner.

</what>

<how>

An online BIM editor is used with modelo architecture application with templates of food plot miyawaki landscaping, allowing a user to use the default BIM Files or create a basic customization with written requirements.

BIM Objects for the plant list of Lakeshore Preserve are generated,

BIM Objects , a downloadable repository of objects has the following assets.

Size I to V plant assets.

</how>

<why>

Food Forestry and Food Plot engineering form a large market share in the landscaping and forestry market, with potential growth in indigenous conservation and habitat fragmentation for wildlife.

Headstarting several threatened species of flora and fauna may be possible with the Miyawaki approach as the primary habitat needed by these endangered species may be restored, migration corridors may be restored as a side effect of habitat defragmentation.

The adoption of food forestry in urban areas, and the creation of food plots in areas on forest peripheries, may create urban zones of conservation, as prescribed by Akira Miyawaki.

From a developmental perspective, it is a win-win scenario with restoration as the culmination of the engineering sciences, with a potential for more than a 10% stake in the 13.8 Billion landscaping industry predictions for 2022 in Canada.^{2 2}

Primitivism and a return to natural technologies, with examples ranging from mirror and crystal computing buried in erstwhile westernized sciences like metal metal oxide computing devices and mirror sciences and liquid nitrogen based propulsion engineering, another branch of cryogenics. Several intentional communities have adopted primitivistic technologies, ranging from Amish, to Pagan and Indigenous American sciences.

</why>

Applications:

Food Plot Planning, as Miyawaki Landscape Architecture.

Code Base:

[miyawaki-landscaping-a-quiz](#)

Introduction.

Problem Definition.

The Popcorn, Pizza and Source Code model for the restoration of Oak Savannas, with mixed grassland and open forest vegetation, in a Miyawaki design is formalized in the context of plant groups and miyawaki landscaping with Mapillary for seamless segmentation and the PlantNet App for species identification and Miyawaki Level determination.

Food Forestry with native popcorn corn species and food foresting with Vegan Oak Acorn based pizza recipes with vegetables and Vegan Cheese toppings as a metaphor for permaculture based agro dendrology and ecological spirituality.

Ecological spirituality can only be spiritual if the Forest is a primary forest. The philosophy of Miyawaki.

Background.

BIM or object assets for building planning are beneficial in the context of miyawaki engineered forests as they are traditionally

beside parking lots, factories and pockets of green spaces, surprisingly primary in foliage and size. The forests are extended to rural and forest settings, where landscaping for food plots and food forests, can help bridge habitats for wildlife, and create better sustainable food security.

Object models for landscape planning on the Mutter Gottlich website is a consultancy service of collaborative landscaping with BIM objects with species tags in five levels of the Miyawaki forest with species tags, with automated plant grouping in verno generation.

Philosophy of Akira Miyawaki.

“May the force be with you”, in a new Jedi religion, or restoration, of that very force of nature , of that star Helios, closest to us, is the neo-heliocentrism, an engineering of native flora based forestry, with restorative ecology and agroforestry practices, several practitioners have practiced the technique of the green space as beyond the last shangri la, the return to an engineered human approximation of primary forests - completed by nature itself.

Technology

The use of seamless segmentation techniques such as deep neural networks and Transformers leads to a need for technology, based on web2 or web3 technologies, Mapillary is one such service, open source with source code to segment plants, identify them with PlantNet API and classify the size and plant grouping statistical data, a dynamic grouping that optimized human effort in landscaping.

Natural Genomic Conservation.

Popcorn Corn Heirlooms.

Fig 1: Heirloom Popcorn, Jowar Popcorn, courtesy pepkitchen.com

Pizza from Oak Acorn flour, vegan bean based cheese and native vegetables.

Fig 1: Representative Pizza, courtesy unsplash.com ,

Oak Acorn Flour is an example of a permaculture product with indigenous roots from Europe, Americas and Asia. The pizza, a modern food and part of the coding and design culture is instrumental in bridging the digital divide towards goals of decolonization and restoration, the Miyawaki Landscaping.

Other ingredients required are easily incorporated in several layers of the Miyawaki.

Earth Peace.

“Earth Peace, in Japaneseアースピース
Āsupīsu,³
in Ojibwe,
Ahki Wijiindwin.

The new era of decolonized restoration
dawns with the light of a renewed
Hiroshima, the hollow human arrogance
shamed in a green canopy where once
a crater stood from a nuclear holocaust.
As you soon forget the horrors of human
making, to realize that Earth Peace now
reigns, in a downhill drive.

Join the force of nature, be the force as
the crypto Earth Peace, a coin of peace
and downhill decolonized restoration is
discovered, a blockchain from the code
units of floral digital twins, that
omnipresent green space, for the planet,
the carbon credits, the carbon sink, the
restoration equations.”

Code Units or CU, are aspects of the
machine genome in the metaverse that
symbolize digital twins, and DPA with
RAVATTT⁴, an application of the
dog-ears theorem.⁵

Blockchain thus stores the blueprint of
life, as a machine genome for the digital
twins in the metaverse. The most
appropriate blockchain for the C.U, is to
be determined. This is a topic of future
research into quantum cryptography as
web3 for a blueprint.

Discussion.

The Earth Peace, a coin sculpture available
on KalkiChapel, on Shapeways represents
downhill decolonized restoration, in akira
Miyawaki’s philosophy of being one with the

forces of nature, or restorative ecology,
when it is profitable in the metaverse, to
automate and restore, the druidic and
droidic sciences, not a polluting alien
science.

While the Earth embraces you in a green
beckoning as you belong to this planet, one
with the land, seas and sky.

Future Work.

Code Units, or CU are an atomicity of a
newer quantum web3 architecture to
archive the genome of the digital twins in
the metaverse, based on automation from
statefulness, a universe based on
automation with digital process automation,
a process automation with a genome for
scaffolding engineering and transcriptional
engineering, this code unit translates to a
blockchain capital that is defined in a
quantum virtual machine.

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